

Saints, Ancestors and Ashes

Open Semantic Networks from Holy Wells and Ogham Inscriptions to the Campanian Ignimbrite

Florian Thiery, Fiona Schenk, Peter Thiery

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Panel: Casting the Net Wide

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Casting the Net Wide: An open, semantic approach for modelling cultural and spatial networks in archaeology

**OGHAM
INSCRIPTIONS**

**HOLY
WELLS**

**THE CAMPANIAN
INGIMBRITE
ERUPTION**

Case studies from Archaeology, Cultural Heritage and Geosciences:
Ogham Inscriptions, Holy Wells, and the Campanian Ignimbrite eruption

The Use Cases represent networks — genealogical, devotional, and geological — unified through Linked Open Data (LOD) principles and implemented within the Wikibase ecosystem

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

How to “feed” the (CH-) **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem?**

FAIR access to Cultural Heritage data plays a crucial role in fostering transparency, reproducibility, and community engagement

The Ogham inscriptions of Ireland encode person networks through early medieval kinship formula words inscribed in stone

The Irish Holy Wells dataset maps saint networks that link sacred water sources with local devotional traditions and Christianisation processes

The Campanian Ignimbrite eruption, originating from the Phlegraean Fields in Italy, forms a spatial network of volcanic ash deposits and archaeological findspots across Europe

All three datasets are aligned via CIDOC CRM, PROV-O, and GeoSPARQL, creating interoperable, queryable knowledge graphs

This captures semantic meaning in each relationship – *isDedicatedTo*, *descendedFrom*, *wasDepositedAt* – enabling transparent, machine-actionable exploration across social, sacred, and spatial domains

The result is a reproducible, FLOSS-based and FAIR-compliant workflow that demonstrates how LOD and Wikibase can bridge disciplines

This method offers a transferable Open Science framework for integrating archaeological, historical, and geoscientific networks

Ogham Stones

Ancestors Network

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

(C) OpenStreetMap contributors
Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ogham! 4.-6. AD, early Medieval, “Primitive Irish”

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

OPEN SCIENCE FELLOWS PROGRAM

wmde.org/opensciencefellows

Ogham Stones within the KG Ecosystem

Extract from the Linked Open Ogham Ontology

"MAQI" (engl: son, Q67381254)
"MUCOI" (engl: tribe; ir: túath, Q67999759),
"NIOTA" (engl: nephew, sister`s son)

"CATTU" (engl: battle, Q67383338)
"ERC" (engl: god, Q67382360)
"DALAGNI" (engl: blind, Q68001812)

The Ogham inscriptions of early medieval Ireland and Scotland are notable for their use of formula words for relationships

via <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400178>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network | [Linked Ogham](#)

[@dovinias](#) EN

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400178>

The **dovinias** resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
label_upper	<ul style="list-style-type: none">DOVINIAS (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)DOVINIAS (rdf:langString) (iso639:goid)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept (skos:Concept) [x]Person (oghamonto:Person) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">dovinias (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)dovinias (rdf:langString) (iso639:goid)
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">dovinias (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)dovinias (rdf:langString) (iso639:goid)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept Instances Collection (fsld:Concept_collection)Person Instances Collection (fsld:Person_collection)

via <http://lwaid.org/cisndb/name/dovinias>

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): GRAVICASMAQI | MUCOI[DO]VINAS

Expansion:

GRAVICAS MAQI MUCOI [DO]VINAS

[Gravicas](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Dovinias](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): CUNAMAQQICORBBIMAQQ ||| [--] ||| [--]S

Expansion:

CUNAMAQQI CORBBI MAQQI MUCCOI DOVINIAS

[Cunamaqqi Corbbi](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

See McManus/1991, 102, 107.

[\[Dovinia\]s](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Macalister, R.A.S. (1897): MAQQI IARIKIMA ||| QQI ||| MUCCOIDOVINIAS

Expansion:

MAQQI-IARIKI MAQQI MUCCOI DOVINIAS

[Maqqi-Iari](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Dovinias](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

See McManus/1991, 111, states that all examples of this name, except one, are from Corkaguiney.

tribe: doviniias

Dovinias (BALIG/3) [Dovinia]s (BALIG/7) Dovinias (BLTAG/2)

via <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400278>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network | Linked Ogham

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400287>

The luguni resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Property	Value
label_upper	<ul style="list-style-type: none">LUGUNI (rdflangString) (iso639:en)LUGUNI (rdflangString) (iso639:goide)
type (rdftype)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept (skos:Concept) [x]Person (oghamonto:Person) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">luguni (rdflangString) (iso639:en)luguni (rdflangString) (iso639:goide)
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">luguni (rdflangString) (iso639:en)luguni (rdflangString) (iso639:goide)
Is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept Instances Collection (fsid:Concept_collection)Person Instances Collection (fsid:Person_collection)

tribe: luguni

Luguni (WINDG/1) Luguni (KNWEE/2) Luguni (CSKEE/1) Luguni (KNWEE/1)

via <http://w3id.org/cisqdb/name/luguni>

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): MODDAGN[] MAQIGATT [] | AGNI [] [] | MUCOILUGUNI

Expansion:

MODDAGN[] MAQI GATTAGN[] MUCOI LUGUNI

[Moddagn\[i\]](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

M^{ad}n, 'Noble?', McManus/1991, 107.

[Gattagn\[i\]](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

G^{eth}n, McManus/1991, 107.

[Luguni](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Tribal name *D^l Luigni*, McManus/1991, 111-2.

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): VEQI{X}A[M^B] IMAQILUGUNI

Expansion:

VEQIKAMI MAQI LUGUNI

[Veqikami](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Luguni](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): [COV]AGNIMAQ [] | I[] MU [] | COI[] LUG[] UNI[]

Expansion:

[COV]AGNI MAQI [MUCOI] LUG[] UNI[]

Covagni (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

McManus/1991, 107, states that the suffix -AGNI > ANNI is diminutive and also very common on Ogham inscriptions.

McManus/1991, 111-112, further argues that this person, as a result of their sept name, may have been a member of the Luigni of Meath.

Ziegler/1994, 156, argues for this being the genitive singular of an O-stem with the diminutive suffix *-gno-, and that in Old Irish this name gave Cuan.

Luguni (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

McManus/1991, 108, sees this name as possibly having a nasal suffix and that Luguni gave Luigne.

McManus/1991, 111-112: 'LUGUNI [D^l Luigni] ... the Luigni are associated mainly with Connacht and Meath.'

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): [M]I[C]ANAVVI MAQ L[U]G[U]N[]

Expansion:

[M]I[C]ANAVVI MAQ L[U]G[U]N[]

[Micanavvi](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Luguni](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

via <http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400090>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Linked Ogham

 coimagni_{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OP400090>

The **coimagni** resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
label_upper	<ul style="list-style-type: none">COIMAGNI (rdflangString) (iso6391:en)COIMAGNI (rdflangString) (iso6391:goide)
type (rdftype)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept (skos:Concept) [x]Person (oghamonto:Person) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">coimagni (rdflangString) (iso6391:en)coimagni (rdflangString) (iso6391:goide)
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">coimagni (rdflangString) (iso6391:en)coimagni (rdflangString) (iso6391:goide)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Concept Instances Collection (fslid:Concept_collection)Person Instances Collection (fslid:Person_collection)

Macalister, Robert Alexander Stewart. 1945. *Corpus Inscriptionum Insularum Celticarum*. Dublin: Stationery Office.

via <http://w3id.org/cispdb/name/coimaeni>

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): COIMAG{N}I | F/IL/I | CAVETI

Expansion:

COIMAGNI **FILI** CAVETI

Coimagni (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Rhys/1889, 312: 'The name *Coimagni* (in Irish *Coemhan*) is a derivative from *coim*, in Old Irish *coem*, later *coemh*, Welsh *cu*, dear, beloved'.

Jackson/1953, 312: 'unquestionably Irish, not British ... the common OI. name *Coem*↔n'.

Caveti (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Rhys/1889, 312: 'The genitive *Caveti* is of the same origin as the *cav* in the *Cavo* of the Llanfor Stone, and the *Burgocavi* of the lost Caeragi Stone'.

Macalister, R.A.S. (1897): COIMAGNIMAQIVI || | TALIN

Expansion:

COIMAGNI **MAQI** VITALIN

Coimagni (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Macalister 1897/47: 'The name *Coimagni* meets us again in Roman letters on one of the stones at Llandello, in Pembroke. It is the *Coman* of the Martyrology of Donegal and the Four Masters'.

See McManus/1991, 107.

Vitalin (Language: Latin; Gender: male)

Macalister 1897/47: '*Vitalin*, the Middle Irish *Fidlin*, is found at Cwm Gloyn in the form *Vitalin*'.

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): COIMAGNIMAQIMOCOIGA[--

Expansion:

COIMAGNI **MAOI MOCOI** GA[--

Coimagni (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

name: coimagni

Coimagni (LDEIL/2) Coimagni (BLHER/1) Coimagni (AHLIS/3)

Holy Wells

Saints Network

Table - 25 Ergebnisse in 1876 ms </> Code Herunter

item	ItemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed
Q:121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well		Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcd3a3204744a33b2255465028b8>
Q:126448724	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.4730101 52.7209032)	8517818852	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/clomanagh-lobermurry-02f47554c604a8b8665ea1bc009fd5>
Q:126649228	Lacken Well		Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5beb9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582>
Q:126487120	St Coleman's Well		Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinson-st-colmans-well-low-poly-fae5988530c648aea73cfd09663954a0>
Q:122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well		Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f79e64b434a6ea08672629b493d>
Q:122304309	Saint Molin's Well (Mullennakil)		Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfff49b2f3d4348d5cade4f869ad33>
Q:126456441	Columbkille's Well		Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40cfa4f0437c698ac7f5>
Q:126454844	Lady's Well		Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bcf22e184897a5b8e758cf7249e>
Q:114439798	Kenny's Well		Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e22263342cfc3>
Q:126458702	St. Nicholas's Well (Killamery)		Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae58dff8da>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9888a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival 2		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9888a0bb3c42029df69>
Q:129263926	Holy Well		Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-jeipoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec40c7430ccbf448869>
Q:126374490	Trinity Well		Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3cd851>
Q:122302608	St. Kieran's Well		Point(-7.3800887 52.3975027)	10544065862	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/whitechurch-kilkieran-st-kierans-well-8cdea3b21314058eb7b69faca418d76>
Q:121840779	St. Lachtain's Well		Point(-7.38951 52.7316)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14daa74d33bb076407134e81e>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>
Q:122189562	Saint Augustine's Well		Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fa14a189a1a59d2e123b1e4>
Q:126456468	Holy Cross well		Point(-7.0437511 52.4878257)	8513475323	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilcross-holy-cross-well-low-poly-ca165580c28429392b1a06491333148>
Q:126657210	St. David's Well		Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144739129	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2ae79bb6ab7c69a8>
Q:126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well		Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8a3147ecb29f367>
Q:126487358	St Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3565632 52.6115585)	8517798092	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/toberbreedia-st-brigid-well-56e71b0735fc4f17bdf3e84c5b2a12a7>
Q:126454422	St Leonard's Well		Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690>

Holy Wells having Sketchfab Links to 3D-Models

holy wells by etymology

etymology	etymologyLabel	count
Q wd:Q345	Mary	24
Q wd:Q2151232	townland	15
Q wd:Q80979	Brigid of Kildare	11
Q wd:Q2280421	Ciarán of Saigir	10
Q wd:Q165479	Saint Patrick	8
Q wd:Q10884	tree	7
Q wd:Q380356	True Cross	7
Q wd:Q16970	church building	6
Q wd:Q953927	Fiacre	5
Q wd:Q107257053	clootie tree	5
Q wd:Q45581	Archangel Michael	4
Q wd:Q44269	Saint Nicholas	4

via <https://www.wiki/ANSc>

Holy Wells by etymology

via <https://wiki/GHHV>

Mary

via <https://skfb.lv/oWCiX>

via <https://wiki/GHHV>

Brigit of Kildare

via <https://skfb.lv/oaFYq>

via <https://wiki/GHHV>

St. Patrick

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Holy Wells around Kilkenny

Master of Jean Rolin II, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Fiacre [Collapse]
 Irish saint

Sant Fiachra, pátrún na n-garraíodóirí

Upload media ↗

Wikipedia ↗

Date of birth 607 (statement with Gregorian date earlier than 1584) Ireland

Date of death 668 (statement with Gregorian date earlier than 1584) Meaux

Place of burial Meaux Cathedral

Country of citizenship Dál Riata

Authority control [Collapse]

Q953927

VIAF ID: 57743610 ↗

GND identifier: 131360958 ↗

Oxford Biography Index Number: 9378 ↗

Reasonator ↗ • Scholia ↗ • Wikidocumentaries ↗ • PeiScan ↗ • statistics ↗ • WikiMap ↗ • Locator tool ↗ • KML file ↗ • Search depicted ↗

Saint Fiachra's Well [Collapse]
 holy well in the townland of Sheestown/Sheestown, Co. Kilkenny

Upload media ↗

Instance holy well

of Holy Well Semantic Concept

Concept holy well (2023, in use)

Named after Fiacre

Location County Kilkenny
 Kilferagh
 Ireland

Diocese Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory

Collection Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II Survey of Holy Wells County Kilkenny Phase 1 and Phase 2. A report prepared for Kilkenny County Council Heritage Office as an action of the Kilkenny Heritage Plan, 2024

Inventory number 166 (Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II) KH/ND44 (Survey of Holy Wells County Kilkenny Phase 1 and Phase 2. A report prepared for Kilkenny County Council Heritage Office as an action of the Kilkenny Heritage Plan, 2024)

Authority control [Collapse]

Q121842432

OpenStreetMap node ID: B515205450 ↗

Reasonator ↗ • Scholia ↗ • Wikidocumentaries ↗ • PeiScan ↗ • statistics ↗ • WikiMap ↗ • Locator tool ↗ • KML file ↗ • WikishootMap ↗ • OpenStreetMap ↗ • Search depicted ↗

via <https://irelandsholywells.blogspot.com/2012/07/saint-fiachras-well-kilkenny.html>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Saint Fiachra's Well in Kilferagh, County Kilkenny, Ireland

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/pq67u>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Sheestown Townland: St Fiachra's Well

Dictionary of National Biography, 1885-1900/Lachtain

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←Lacey, William

Dictionary of National Biography, 1885-1900, Volume 31

Lackington, George→

Lachtain by Norman Moore

Lachtáin mac Tarbín in the *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*.

[sister projects: Wikidata item](#)

^[369] **LACHTAIN** (d. 622), Irish saint, whose name also appears in Irish literature as Laichtin (*Martyrology of Donegal*, p. 80), Lachtnain (*Annala Rioghachta Éireann*, i. 244), Lachtoc, and Molachtoc (*Felire Cengusa*, ed. Stokes, pp. 57, 64), belonged to the tribe called Muscraighe, who claimed descent from Coaire Mac Modhlamha, a king of Ireland in the second century. His father's name was Torben, and he was born in Munster. He became a disciple of Comgall [q. v.] of Beannchair and founded two churches, one in Ossory at Achadh-úr, now Freshford, county Kilkenny, the other at Bealach Feabhradh, of which the site is now uncertain. A later church, with an Irish inscription of the eleventh century over the door, represents his earlier edifice at Freshford, and near it is a holy well, called after him Tobar Lachtain. He died in 622. In the museum of the Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, is a silver reliquary, made in the twelfth century, to contain an arm of this saint. His feast is celebrated 19 March.

[Colgan's *Acta Sanctorum Hiberniæ*; *Martyrology of Donegal*, Irish Archæological and Celtic Society, 1864; O'Donovan's note in *Annala R. E.*, i. 244–5; *Leabhar Breac*, facs. fol. 83; *Dunraven's Notes on Irish Architecture*, 1877, ii. 91; *Mo Turas ar Lachtain*, 1877.]

N. M.

Saint Fiachra's Well in Kilferagh, County Kilkenny, Ireland

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

Campanian Ignimbrite

Ashes Network

About 40'000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

fuzzy-sf RDF Modelling Scheme

fuzzy-sl Wikibase Modelling Scheme

Findspots with *spatial-type: Cave* and *Archaeological Site*

Figure 7. Selection of retouched bladelets from 'rsa' and 'gic'. Additional photos of retouched bladelets from 'gic' and 'rsa' can be found in Supplementary Figs. S14-S15. The number following the alphabetical list corresponds to the ID assigned by AF during the techno-typological analysis (refer to the provided dataset for details). Tools are sorted by the position of the retouch: direct: bilateral retouch (a, c-f, h-p, s, and v), direct unilateral (b, g, and u), inverse (q), and alternate (r and t). Photos by A. Falucci.

Falucci, Armando, Simona Arrighi, Vincenzo Spagnolo, Matteo Rossini, Owen Alexander Higgins, Brunella Muttillo, Ivan Martini, et al. 2024. 'A Pre-Campanian Ignimbrite Techno-Cultural Shift in the Aurignacian Sequence of Grotta Di Castelcivita, Southern Italy'. *Scientific Reports* 14 (1): 12783. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59896-6>

Oertle, Annette, Jacopo Czezzini, Adriana Moroni, Annamaria Ronchitelli, Stefano Benazzi, Armando Falucci, Giulia Marciani, et al. 2025. 'New Insights from the Application of ZooMS to Late Pleistocene Fauna from Grotta Di Castelcivita, Southern Italy'. *Scientific Reports* 15 (1): 25906. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-11355-6>

Fig. 5. Newly identified taxa from originally unidentified fragmented bones. (a) CLE0043 Canid from spH 14. (b) CLE036 Canid from spH 38. (c) CLE072 Ursid from spH 27. (d) CLE048 Ursid from spH 28. (e) CLE044 Ursid from spH 38. (f) CLE076 Rhino from spH 24. (g) CLE065 Rhino from spH 25.

<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/337519639>

Castelcivita Cave in literature and OpenStreetMap

Castelcivita Cave EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_5

The Castelcivita Cave resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	high (fsl:high) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2008 (rdf:string) Giaccio et al., 2008 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsphas:Geometry)	cisite_5_geom (fsl:cisite_5_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (fsl:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Castelcivita Cave (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 337519639 (337519639) [x] Q3777120 (wikidata:Q3777120) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Castelcivita Cave (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_5_activity (fsl:cisite_5_activity)

Item Discussion

Castelcivita Cave (Q117)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
Italian	Castelcivita		
English	Castelcivita Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site Archaeological Site
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2008 Giaccio et al., 2008
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology Geology
has coordinate	<p>45°29'44.27"N 15°12'23.11"E</p> <p>certainty level: High</p> <p>certainty description: findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap</p> <p>method used: GeoReferencing</p> <p>acting person: Flavia Schenk</p> <p>source type (generic): Textual Description</p> <p>source type (detail): Paper</p> <p>method description: CI findspot related from literature at 0001"</p> <p>precision: findspot</p> <p>location type: findspot</p> <p>point type: Natural Place</p> <p>+ 1 reference</p> <p>reference (string): Fedele et al., 2008</p> <p>Giaccio et al., 2008</p>

Castelcivita Cave in the LOD Cloud

Fig. 3. Grotta Paglicci; Flint industry.

<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/2293681037>

Node: Grotta Paglicci (2293681037)
Version #7

removed site_type= transitional simultaneous tagging with archaeological_site=, as discussed in <https://community.openstreetmap.org/t/implementation-of-new-tagging-scheme-of-archaeological-site/7050>

Edited over 2 years ago by ChillyDL
ChangeSet #138536810
Location: 41.6541150, 15.6149763

Tags	Value
access	no
archaeological_site	rock_painting
historic	archaeological_site
historiccivilization	prehistoric
name	Grotta Paglicci
wikidata	Q3777010
wikipedia	it:Grotta Paglicci

Download XML

Node / History / Versions:
1 2 3 4 5 6

Zorzi, F. 1964. 'Palaeolithic Discoveries in the Grotta Paglicci'. *Antiquity* 38 (149): 38-44. doi: [10.1017/S0003598X00068757](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00068757)
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Paglicci Cave in literature and OpenStreetMap

Paglicci Cave EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_19

The **Paglicci Cave** resource is powered by Static **GeoPubby** generated using the **SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin**

Search: Format:

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	Giaccio et al., 2008 (xsd:string) [x]
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_19_geom (fsl:cisite_19_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (placodes:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
label (rdfs:label)	Paglicci Cave (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2293681037 (2293681037) [x] Q3777010 (wikidata:Q3777010) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Paglicci Cave (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_19_activity (fsl:cisite_19_activity)

Item Discussion

Paglicci Cave (Q114)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

in other languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Paglicci Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site 0 references Archaeological Site 0 references
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots 0 references
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave 0 references
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giaccio et al., 2008 0 references
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology 0 references Geology 0 references
has coordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 41°39'14.87"N, 15°36'54.0"E certainty level: Medium certainty description: Findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap method used: Georeferencing acting person: Flavia Schenk source type (generic): Textual Description source type (detail): Paper method description: CI findspot related from literature precision: ±0.0001° location type: Findspot point type: Natural Place 1 reference reference (String): Giaccio et al., 2008

Paglicci Cave in the LOD Cloud

To conclude ...

... and open for discussion ...

Open Science offers a lot potential to analyse archaeological, historical, and geoscientific networks.

Finis!

Thx!

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